

Using the Hofstede's Organizational Culture Framework to Measure the Feasibility of Tourist Sites: Tourist Satisfaction Analysis

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Abstract:- This study aims to measure the feasibility of tourist sites through tourist perceptions. Hofstede's dimension was chosen as the instrument because of its superiority in measuring cultural attributes which were previously sporadic and difficult to define behavior, attitudes, and characteristics in general. This study uses a descriptive method with a quantitative approach, and involves 399 tourists as respondents. The results of the study found that tourists assess the feasibility of a tourist attraction based on their respective cultural backgrounds. Foreign tourists will assess the feasibility of a tourist attraction based on the use of language. Female travelers assess eligibility based on safety aspects. Some tourists even assess the feasibility of the taste aspect of the food traded. The research findings also show that Hofstede's organizational culture framework can be used as an instrument in measuring the feasibility of tourism objects in terms of cultural attributes that have been neglected because they are intangible and sporadic. The results of empirical measurements using Hofstede's five dimensions can support secondary data as a database in the preparation of tourism development policy frameworks in the future. The results of this study form the basis that the development of tourism objects in the future must consider cultural dimensions such as gender and language as well as ethnic background.

Keywords:- Organizational Culture; Feasibility; Tourist Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The condition of tourism in Gorontalo is still dominated by domestic tourists. However, there has been a decrease in the number of visitors over the last few periods due to the Corona pandemic. It was recorded that the number of domestic tourist visits reached 1,304,254 people in 2019 and 403,097 people in 2020, while foreign tourists reached 11,173 people in 2019 and 1,223 people in 2020. This number was followed by data on hotel occupancy rates which were only able to reach 29.065% in 2020 after previously being in the range of 30.81% in 2019 (Statistik, 2021). Entering the period of economic recovery, the local government is working with stakeholders to prepare a digital-based database to increase promotion and tourist visits, and some of which are of concern are natural tourist sites such as beach tourism, hot springs, and marine parks (Humas Pemprov Gorontalo, 2022).

The location of Gorontalo which is on the line of Tomini Bay, positions it in a geographical area that has the potential to be used as a natural tourist destination. If developed, this could be one of the primary sectors driving the regional economy apart from agriculture and marine affairs (Bayih & Singh, 2020). This is as stated by Job & Paesler (2013) in their research that the unique environment and natural potential have a positive impact on the economy and create jobs for local communities. Thus, the use of nature as a tourist destination is an alternative to attract people to visit (Chung et al., 2018). However, to be able to provide satisfaction to tourists, nature-based tourist sites must also be supported by the availability of supporting facilities and infrastructure (Hossain & Khanal, 2020).

Tourist satisfaction indicators are always measured from physical aspects such as the availability of supporting facilities. Meanwhile, on the one hand, there are non-physical aspects that cannot be ignored (Sedarmayanti, 2017). The physical condition of tourist sites is indeed able to provide satisfaction through comfort, because it creates a good mood in visitors (Mayhoub & Rabboh, 2022), but to support positioning and shape tourist perceptions, non-physical aspects need to be encouraged because with this the quality of service is very important perceived to exceed tourist expectations (Kotler & Armstrong, 2016).

The non-physical dimensions that affect satisfaction in the world of business strategy have been investigated empirically, one of the non-physical factors that are considered important to study is organizational culture (Pearce, 2016). Lund (2003) in his research measures satisfaction using Cameron and Freeman's organizational culture model with a conceptual framework that includes indicators of clan, adhocracy, hierarchy, and market. His findings reveal that the level of satisfaction varies depending on the typology of organizational culture. A study conducted by Huang & Crofts (2019) at tourist sites in Australia and Hong Kong revealed that tourist satisfaction is also influenced by the dimensions of organizational culture, in this case the region/country. Based on this, the manager of local tourist sites must also understand the characteristics of their visitors (Bayih & Singh, 2020). The same thing was also conveyed by Hauff et al (2015) in their research that organizational culture affects employee job satisfaction, so leaders need to understand the characteristics of each employee, especially those with expatriate status.

Based on this description, the researcher tries to see the satisfaction of tourists in Gorontalo from the perspective of organizational culture. The benchmark used is using Hofstede's organizational culture dimensions. The Hofstede dimension was chosen on the basis of its superiority in measuring cultural attributes which were previously sporadic and difficult to define behavior, attitudes, and characteristics of society in general (Ferreira et al., 2014). Hofstede's dimensions include power of distance, individualism vs. collectivism, masculinity vs. femininity, uncertainty avoidance, long vs. short-term orientation (Djekic et al., 2021). In their research, Djekic et al., (2021) measure consumer satisfaction in choosing food, and the results show that consumers' cultural background influences their food choices. This also underlies researchers in measuring tourist satisfaction using Hofstede's dimensions. It is hoped that the measurement results can be a reference in formulating a tourism area management strategy from a local to cross-cultural perspective.

This research was conducted on the basis of the gap from previous research related to the conceptual framework used. Mueller-Bloch & Kranz (2015) explain that the conceptual gap is one of the types of research gaps that can be used as a basis for conducting research. The research gap departs from the development of previous research models that only use physical indicators in measuring satisfaction. In this study, the dimension of satisfaction used is Hofstede's organizational culture framework.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Culture and Tourist Satisfaction

In the context of tourism, Battour et al (2012) state that satisfaction is a reaction that arises after evaluating the tourist sites visited. tourist destinations are given in the form of recognition. Another opinion was put forward by Chen & Tsai (2007) that satisfaction is about the extent of the pleasure felt by tourists resulting from the ability of tourism to fulfill the desires, expectations, and needs of tourists. When the attributes of a tourist destination meet or exceed the wishes of visitors, tourists will experience a pleasant experience (Baker & Crompton, 2000).

Tourist satisfaction is also stated to have a positive correlation with the quality of the tourist experience at the destination location (Lee, 2007). Based on this opinion, it can be concluded that tourist satisfaction is an important issue for managers and local communities in managing tourist destinations (Ngoc & Trinh, 2015). Some research results also agree that favorable satisfaction leads to positive future behaviors such as increased intention to revisit and higher willingness to recommend to others (Bayih & Singh, 2020; Chen & Tsai, 2007).

a) Power of Distance

Hofstede said that power distance is the extent to which members of less powerful institutions and organizations in a country expect and accept that power is distributed unequally (Thowfeek & Jaafar, 2012). In this study, the POD dimension is used to measure how tourists perceive natural tourism sites in Gorontalo based on the availability of services that are

responsive to persons with disabilities, gender, children, and tourism actors with low budgets (backpackers).

b) Individualism vs Collectivism

Hofstede said that individualism is related to how a person or group behaves at work. The culture of individualism leads to a condition in which a person is only interested in working alone or only with those closest to him. Meanwhile, collectivism tends to be open to accepting members from outside the circle (Thowfeek & Jaafar, 2012). In this study, the individualism aspect is used to measure the extent to which the participation of managers and local communities in mingling with visitors. This participation includes the availability of tour guides, community skills in communicating with local and foreign visitors, as well as the level of security of tourist sites for tourists traveling alone, especially women.

c) Masculinity vs Feminism

Hofstede explains that masculinity tends to be achievement-oriented or material success, while femininity is oriented to people or quality of life (Thowfeek & Jaafar, 2012). In this study, the MF dimension is used to measure the feasibility of tourist sites starting from the availability of brochures, food choices, access to information about transportation, as well as tourist perceptions regarding the application of different rental fees.

d) Uncertainty Avoidance

Hofstede defines uncertainty avoidance as the extent to which members feel threatened by or anxious by ambiguous and unknown situations. This dimension focuses on how culture adapts to change with uncertainty (Thowfeek & Jaafar, 2012). In this study, the UA dimension is used to measure the tendency of tourists to choose supporting elements at tourist sites which include interest in local transportation, the tendency to choose food to be consumed during the trip, representative lodging, and the desire to use tourist equipment.

e) Long vs Short Term Orientation

This point focuses on the degree to which society's long-term adherence to traditional values is concerned. Individuals in long-term orientation cultures look to the future and value thrift, persistence and tradition. Every society must maintain some things related to its past while facing the challenges of the present and the future (Thowfeek & Jaafar, 2012). With regard to tourist satisfaction, this dimension is defined as actions that are in accordance with the rules or norms that apply at tourist sites (short term orientation) and pragmatic actions that prioritize practicality (long term orientation). The LSTO dimension is used to measure the feasibility of tourist sites from aspects related to information regarding applicable norms, the presence or absence of information about local wisdom as an education-based promotional media for tourists, the availability of information boards that use bilingual languages and infrastructure facilities for backpackers.

III. METHOD

This study aims to measure the feasibility of tourist sites based on tourist perceptions as measured using Hofstede's organizational culture dimensions. This research is based on data on the decreasing number of tourist visits to tourist destinations in Gorontalo. In order to encourage the number of tourist visits, researchers consider it necessary to first measure the level of tourist satisfaction in order to identify which aspects need to be intervened and developed. The perspective of Hofstede's organizational culture is the dimension chosen by researchers in making measurements based on research findings by previous researchers. This study uses a descriptive method with a quantitative approach.

The population in this study amounted to 404,320 people. Due to the large population size, the researcher took a sample using the Slovin formula and obtained a sample of 399 respondents with a 5% sampling error. Samples were selected randomly using incidental sampling technique. In this study, the researcher acts as the main instrument, namely adapting to the conditions in the field for research purposes so that the existence of the researcher at the research location is known by the object of research. In addition, researchers are directly involved in the field with the aim of collecting data so that the data collected is truly accurate according to the needs of researchers.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research respondents came from a variety of different cultural backgrounds. The following is a description of the demographic data of the respondents.

Characteristics	Classification	Total	Frequency
Gender	Male	192	48,12
	Female	207	51,88
Country	Local Tourist	361	90,48
	Foreign Tourist	38	9,52
Source of tourist location information	Friend	186	46,62
	Family	143	35,84
	Social Media	49	12,28
	etc	21	5,26

Table 1: Demographic data of the respondents

Source: Questionnaire Data Processed (2022)

The table above shows that the majority of respondents who participated in this study were female tourists, namely 51.88%. The respondents consisted of local tourists 90.48% and foreign tourists 9.52%. The data above also shows that the promotion of tourist objects has not been carried out massively. The existence of social media has not been fully utilized as a tourism promotion medium. Of the total 399 respondents involved, only 12.28% obtained information through social media. The rest is through word of mouth

from friends and family. The remaining 5.26% are tourists who get information while on an official trip. These numbers mean that Gorontalo's tourist attraction is still not able to reach foreign tourists. There needs to be a development that is designed with reference to the database of tourist needs.

Presentation of survey data on the feasibility and needs of tourists measured using Hofstede's five dimensions;

Fig. 1: Respondents' Perceptions Based on the Power of Distance Dimension

(Source: Questionnaire Data, Processed in 2022)

Fig. 2: Average Score Per Aspect of Power of Distance Dimension

(Source: Questionnaire Data, processed 2022)

Figure 1 shows that 80.5% of tourists do not agree if it is said that the condition of tourist sites in Gorontalo is responsive to persons with disabilities. 46.8% disagreed with the statement that tourist sites in Gorontalo were gender responsive. The feasibility test on the child-friendly aspect also showed 34.3% agreed if the tourist sites in Gorontalo had met the child-friendly criteria, and 19.6% said they did not agree. There are also almost no cases of discrimination against backpackers in Gorontalo, as evidenced by the respondents' disapproval rate of 60.6%. In the context of power of distance, if a location cannot accommodate the needs of persons with disabilities and provide adequate facilities from a gender aspect, it will have negative consequences.

Figure 2 explains that the power of distance culture explains how tourism managers and local communities provide a comfortable space for every visitor who comes. Overall, the average respondents' answers to each indicator show that tourist sites in Gorontalo are slightly superior in terms of the feasibility of child-friendly locations. Using a scale of 1-5, the child-friendly aspect obtained a score of 2.92. These results can be used as a basis in determining future tourism development programs. Tourism development programs should focus on providing facilities that are pro-disabilities and gender-based. The level of safety and comfort for children visitors also needs to be improved. Management of tourist sites with a high level of power of distance can have an impact on decreasing the number of visits to these locations.

Fig. 3: Respondents' Perceptions Based on Individualism vs Collectivism Dimensions

(Source: Questionnaire Data, processed in 2022)

Fig. 4: Average Score Per Aspect Dimension of Individualism vs Collectivism

(Source: Questionnaire Data, processed 2022)

Figure 3 shows that the availability of tour guides is still very lacking. 78.4% of tourists stated that the existence of a tour guide is very much needed, considering that the tourist sites in Gorontalo are quite far from lodging places that tend to be in the city center. Local communities also need to be given skill development related to foreign language skills. 76% of respondents said that many people in tourist locations do not know foreign languages. This will certainly make it difficult for foreign tourists to communicate. In addition, local people also need to be trained to use good and correct Indonesian. 48.1% of respondents said that the language skills of local people around tourist sites were only mediocre. Tourist sites also tend to be unsafe for female travelers traveling alone. 58.4% of respondents said they did not agree with the level of security around tourist sites. This is triggered by terrain conditions and access to tourist sites which are quite heavy, and dark at night making them vulnerable to crime.

Figure 4 shows that the availability of tour guides received the highest response from respondents with an average score of 4.14. This indicates that this dimension is most needed by every tourist who visits, especially those from outside Gorontalo. The second aspect is the ability to speak good and correct Indonesian. The number of tourist visits, which are dominated by domestic tourists, causes this aspect to get an average value of 3.14 which indicates that local people still tend to use everyday language/slang. The third aspect that also needs to be taken seriously is the improvement of infrastructure towards tourist sites. The average score of 2.45 indicates that the dimensions get enough attention from the tourists. While the development of foreign language skills for local communities may not be a top priority, it still needs to be stimulated because considering that the target of future promotions is foreign tourists.

Fig. 5: Respondents Perception Based on Masculinity vs Feminism Dimensions

(Source: Questionnaire Data, processed 2022)

Fig. 6: Average Score Per Aspect Dimensions of Masculinity vs. Feminism

(Source: Questionnaire Data, processed 2022)

Figure 5 shows that, 64.2% of respondents admitted that they do not really need brochures as a source of information about tourist locations, this is because tourists seek more information through social media. The application of different rental fees is also necessary in boosting tourism sector revenues. 40.1% of respondents said that there should be a difference in rental fees for local tourists and foreign tourists. Managers of tourist sites also need to pay attention to the culinary aspect. So far, the snacks offered at tourist sites tend to highlight local flavors. On the one hand, 71.4% of tourists want general food choices with Indonesian flavors so that they are easily accepted by their tongues from outside Gorontalo. Regarding transportation, 48.6% of respondents admitted that they had difficulty in obtaining transportation access information. Because tourist locations tend to be far

from lodging centers, most of which are in the city, information on transportation access is needed.

Figure 6 shows that the culinary aspect and the difference in rental costs are the dimensions that get the most attention from tourists. So tourism development can be focused on culinary arrangements to attract visitors. The application of levies is also required at certain locations, such as marine park tourism sites. This is necessary to encourage regional income from the tourism sector. Information related to transportation access and the availability of brochures also needs a little touch through cooperation between the government and inn/hotel owners. Each inn can facilitate the availability of information both regarding access to transportation and information on tourist location profiles through brochure media.

Fig. 7: Respondents' Perceptions Based on Uncertainty Avoidance Dimensions

(Source: Questionnaire Data, processed 2022)

Fig. 8: Average Score per Aspect of Uncertainty Avoidance Dimension

(Source: Questionnaire Data, processed 2022)

Organizations with a high level of uncertainty avoidance tend to avoid innovation because it contains the risk of uncertainty. Through this research, the risk of uncertainty can be avoided through mapping the needs of tourists. Figure 7 shows 56.4% of tourists are more interested in renting a rental vehicle as a means of transportation while traveling in Gorontalo. 46.6% of tourists prefer to buy food at tourist sites rather than bringing their own lunch. 68.9% of tourists look for lodging that is close to tourist sites. 70.1% of tourists prefer to rent tourist equipment on site rather than bring their own equipment. The presentation of the data above is an illustration of what aspects need to be encouraged by the government in developing tourism.

Figure 8 shows that the dimensions of the availability of lodging around the location are aspects that are often sought after by tourists. The existence of lodging around tourist sites is rarely found in Gorontalo. Most of the inns are located in urban areas which tend to be far from tourist sites. Some tourist locations such as beaches do provide accommodation in the form of villas, but in terms of price they are still quite exclusive for most tourists. This is inseparable from the characteristics of tourists from outside who are mostly backpackers.

Fig. 9: Respondents' Perceptions Based on Long vs Short Term Orientation Dimensions

(Source: Questionnaire Data, processed 2022)

Fig. 10: Average Score Per Aspect Dimension Long vs Short Orientation

(Source: Questionnaire Data, processed 2022)

Figure 9 shows that, 80.7% of tourists want information about applicable local norms. As an area that is thick with traditional values, information about local wisdom can be used as an attraction. Issues related to local values can be voiced through promotional media. This information is also a means of education for tourists. 91.5% of respondents also expressed interest in local wisdom in tourist sites, so this is a promotional opportunity. Promotions must also be supported by the availability of information boards containing profiles of tourist sites which are presented in a bilingual manner so that it can be understood by every visitor from various regions or countries. 34.6% of tourists admit that they do not understand the available information, this is because some tourists are foreign tourists who in fact cannot speak Indonesian.

In order to support the promotion, the availability of lodging for backpackers needs serious attention from the government. 82.7% of tourists admitted that they really needed cheap lodging where each room could accommodate several people. In Gorontalo itself, lodging with a backpacker style is still very rare. Lodging that provides bunk bed facilities, needs to be held considering that most foreign tourists who come are backpackers.

The data in Figure 10 shows that the aspect of the availability of special backpackers is the most sought after supporting factor by tourists, especially foreign tourists. So in the context of tourism development, this aspect needs to be increased by the number of units. Then the following, to support promotion, tourism development can also be focused on procuring information media that contains local norms as regional characteristics and of course becomes a special attraction for every visitor who comes on tour.

V. CONCLUSION

Tourism development efforts need to be carried out in order to increase the attractiveness of tourists, especially from outside the region. In order for the development process to be right on target, a database on the factors that influence tourist interest and behavior is needed. The results of the study prove that the cultural background of tourists is an indicator that determines their behavior in choosing tourist locations.

Through Hofstede's organizational culture framework, it was found that a number of cultural dimensions have indications of the feasibility of a tourist attraction. The results of this study form the basis that the development of tourism objects in the future must consider cultural dimensions such as gender and language and ethnic background. From the results of the survey conducted, it was found that tourists

assess the feasibility of a tourist attraction based on their respective cultural backgrounds. Foreign tourists will assess the feasibility of a tourist attraction based on the use of language. Female travelers assess eligibility based on security aspects. Some tourists even judge the feasibility of the taste aspect of the food being traded.

The research findings also show that Hofstede's organizational culture framework can be used as an instrument in measuring the feasibility of tourism objects in terms of cultural attributes that have been overlooked because they are intangible and sporadic. The results of empirical measurements using Hofstede's five dimensions can support secondary data as a database in the preparation of a tourism development policy framework in the future.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

- Tourist sites as public spaces should be able to be enjoyed by everyone, including persons with disabilities, children, and gender responsiveness. Efforts to develop tourism objects can be focused on building facilities for visitors with special needs in order to create tourist sites that are friendly to people with disabilities, gender, and children.
- Recruitment of tour guides at each tourist location through training and certification for tour guides. Strengthening the capacity of the community and managers in terms of foreign language skills in order to support services for tourists from outside the region or foreign tourists. Procurement of supporting facilities such as street lights and improvement of road access to tourist sites so as to give the impression of being safe and comfortable for tourists, especially women who travel alone.
- Government cooperation with hotel/inn management in terms of procurement of brochures and profiles of tourist sites in each hotel. Implement different entry rates or rental fees between local tourists and foreign tourists in order to encourage regional income in each location. Appeal to food vendors to be able to serve food with a variety of menus, both traditional and archipelago. Provide access to information related to transportation facilities at each hotel and tourist location.
- Provide access to vehicle rentals, complete tourist equipment, and build lodging units around tourist areas.
- Maximizing the use of information boards as a medium in promoting local norms and wisdom with a multilingual concept so that every visitor can understand. It is also recommended to be able to increase the number of special backpacker lodging units. This is necessary because considering that Gorontalo is a transit area for foreign tourists, most of whose destinations are Togeian Island.

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